

Human Resource Management

BB 2208

Individual Assignment 2

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Table of Contents

Abstract.....	
Introduction	1
□ Human Resource Management.....	1
□ Standard Casual of HRM.....	1
□ Company Background.....	2
Problem deal by Syarikat AI Rasyid	3
Solution to the problem of Syarikat AI Rasyid	4
Does Standard Casual of HRM helps Syarikat AI Rasyid.....	5
Benefit and Drawbacks of Standard Casual Model of HRM	6
Conclusion	9
References.....	10

Abstract

There are not many young agripreneurs in Brunei Darussalam. In this report we would be analyzing one of the youths of agripreneurs. His name is Muhamad Abdul Rashid bin Kamarudjaman and he owned a business called Syarikat Al Rasyid. For this paper we are finding if, HRM model which is Standard casual of HRM that would be helpful for the Syarikat Al Rasyid and the benefits and drawbacks that can arise from using this model. The Standard casual of HRM model is a well-known model than other models of human resource management. The purpose is to know if the Standard casual of HRM model is suitable with Syarikat Al Rasyid.

Introduction

- Human Resource Management

Human resource management has many different definitions. One of the definitions of human resource management is the organizational role that handles all problems related to the individuals in the organization (Susan M. Heatfield, 2020). This includes the process of recruitment, hiring, performance of the organization, progress of the organization and organization safety. Another definition is from Edwin Flippo (1980) that is human resource management is the process of planning, organizing, managing, monitoring, development, remuneration, maintenance and separation of human resource until individual, organizational and social aims are obtained. Hence, in order to achieve the objective, there is an HRM model or framework that would help the organization to organize and integrate human capital business function. The reason for the HRM model is to assist the companies on how to run their workers in the most well organized and effective manner to achieve the objective.

- Standard Casual of HRM

Standard Casual of HRM is well known and the most outstanding than other models of human resource management (Erik van Vulpen, 2019). This model is extracted from several comparable versions of the HRM model that were released in the 90s and early 2000s. The model displays a causal chain that begins with business procedure and ends, through the HR forms, with improved financial results. As claimed by this model, the HR only be successful if the method is aligned with the business method.

- Company Background

Syarikat Al Rasyid is managed by one person and the owner name is Muhammad Abdul Raysid bin Kamarudjaman. The company was registered on the 4th October 2016. They are an organization that is involved in paddy cultivation. Although the company is registered in 2016, the company began operation in 2015 after he completed the *Belia Berpadi* course. The land he works on is only 1 hectare which is located at MPK Kampung Bebuloh. The owner of Syarikat Al-Rasyid have won *Usahawan Belia Aktif* award in the category of '*Projek Prentis Menggalakan Para Belia Menceburi Pengeluaran Padi Negara*' in the year of 2017. To develop more knowledge in paddy cultivation Rasyid seeks mentors who are farmers that have established paddy businesses. Under the mentorship, there he received many useful information and tips which would help him in managing the farm.

This report will consist about the problem that syarikat al rasyid would be facing, as well as does standard causal HRM models help the organization and what would be the advantages and disadvantages using standard casual hrm models.

Problem deal by Syarikat Al Rasyid

In every business there would be a problem that they need to deal with in order to achieve their goals which is to have a successful business. For Syarikat Al Rasyid they have dealt with a lot of problems. The first problem that they have been facing is regarding the financial resource. The government only gave land to him to start the paddy cultivation. Rasyid is lucky because he was given \$15,000 from LiveWIRE to help him to start the business. Other than that, he also has support from his family that would give him financial backing. Even though he has backing from his family this type of financial resource is not an efficient way to resolve the financial problem. That is why financial resources are important for every business to start up and to avoid having this kind of problem.

Another major problem that the business faces is the land that was given to him by the government. The land has not been inspected whether it is a fertile land or not to cultivate the paddy. So, Rasyid needs to fertilize the soil of the land before to start operating the paddy business. In consequence, the business is delayed which has affected the productivity and rice production. In Brunei the climate is tropical equatorial and humid subtropical and they only have two seasons which are dry season and wet season. From this we can say that Brunei has unpredictable weather which could give problems to Syarikat Al Rasyid in doing their paddy farm.

The last problem that the business is facing is that Rasyid does not have any background in agriculture. So, this can give impact to business performance and how Rasyid do in paddy cultivation. Moreover, in every business knowledge is important which can help the individual to solve the problem in the business. By having no background in agriculture Rasyid could make a wrong judgement in doing the business and this would affect the business in terms of production.

Solution to the problem of Syarikat Al Rasyid

The first problem that Syarikat Al Rasyid deals with is about the financial resource. So, to solve it is by not using the expenses for unnecessary items or items that are no function for the business purpose. For example, in the case of Syarikat Al Rasyid he should only buy items which are important for the business-like equipment for the paddy cultivation. Another way he can get money is from loans through the bank for starting up the business after that avoid loans from the bank to prevent the company from having debts. Companies with many debts would have a bad reputation.

The second problem is about the land that Rasyid receives in not fertilizing enough for paddy cultivation. This leads to low productivity and less rice production. So, to overcome this situation, Rasyid should get help from his mentor and ask if there is any solution that can help him to increase the production and how to fertilize the land. Another solution could be that Rasyid could get a new land which is fertilized enough for him to do the paddy cultivation. This can definitely increase the production of the process, increase the revenue and avoid the delay problem.

The last problem is about Rasyid with no background in agriculture. To resolve this problem Rasyid should seek a mentor which he already did and he gain more knowledge about the paddy cultivation and how to run the business. His mentors were the farmers who have established paddy businesses. His mentor come from *Majlis Perundingan Kampung Limau Manis* in *Ladang Padi Wasan* and *Ladang Padi Bunga Cawan*. Another alternative is to attend more courses in agriculture so, from there he can get motivation in doing his work. This could lead to increase in the performance of the business.

Does Standard Casual of HRM helps Syarikat Al Rasyid

Standard casual HRM model is represented and shows how HR works that is in the same line with organizational strategy could lead to a better business performance. If this standard casual HRM model is implemented to Syarikat Al Rasyid it would definitely improve the performance of the business. But in order to do that the HR of the business needs to be aligned with the business strategy. In other words, they need to be on the same page to improve the performance of the business. HR strategy is obtained from the strategy of the organization thus, it would give a high financial performance.

HR is important to every organization as it is the backbone of the organization. The HR team has a lot of work to do and this is to make sure that the company is functioning well and smooth without any problem. The HR department also needs to come out with an excellent strategy for the workers and to help the workers in the long run. In this model the HR practices follow the HR strategy. For instance, on how they hire, appraisal the individual and compensation. These could lead to good outcomes which include the good commitment, better quality of output and more engagement in the business. So, if Syarikat Al Rasyid follows this model, they can enhance their worker teamwork or individual and can increase the skills of their workers in communication and others.

In addition, this Standard casual HRM model can even lead the business to improve their internal performance. For example, it improves the business productivity, increases innovation and enhances service or product qualities. For this reason, it leads to financial performance. In other words, it can help to generate more revenue and increase profit to the business. In a way if Syarikat Al Rasyid uses this model it could generate more income for the business and this might lead the business to be more successful. Apart from that, the HR practice can also lead to improved internal performance. The illustration is that better training can result in better performance, this can be without the influence from HR outcomes.

From all the evidence above, the standard casual of the HRM model can help Syarikat Al Rasyid. Mostly in increasing the internal performance which could lead to generating more revenue for the business. This can only happen if the HR of the business is on the same page with the business strategy. In general, this HR model explains how a human resource strategy is structured and the implication of human resources on the organizational process and organizational financial performance.

Benefit and Drawbacks of Standard Casual Model of HRM

These Standard casual models of HRM are only suitable for use by companies whose HR team is on the same page with the strategy of the business. Here are some benefit of implementing Standard casual model of HRM in the organization: -

- HR function would involve in strategic decision-making

This point of view says that with the present of HR in this process promotes a better alignment of HR activities with key success factors, thus promoting enhancing the competitive advantage of a company. In other words, the more HR participates in decision-making, the more strategic decisions incorporate the HR role.

- Enhance internal performance

Internal performance is used to measure and monitor the internal operation of an organization. These are indicators of processes in essence. For example in manufacturing organizations they measure the use of equipment, the set up times, work on progress levels and so on.

- Increase Profit Margin

According to Francesca Archive (2019) profit margin is a metric that should be on the radar of every organization because it can tell us whether the organization is making money or otherwise making a loss. Moreover, it should tell us whether the pricing for the service or product is correct or not. Because of internal performance is increasing for example from productivity, innovation and qualities this leads to the increase of profit margin.

- Enhance financial Performance

From the study of Will Kenton (2020) this financial performance is to measure how well the organization can use their assets from its business and generate revenue. The term financial performance is used to measure the organization overall financial health over the given period of time. With the improvement of internal performance from using this model the financial performance also increases.

Regardless the benefit of Standard casual model of HRM there would be some drawback in using this model such as: -

- Not in the same direction

This model has reversed causality, which means that a stronger financial performance often leads to more HR practice and better HR results. So, employees are more active when output is high. If an organization is not on the same page there would be a problem arise. This can impact the organization's performance. For example, if in the meeting the organization would not accomplish their goals.

- Only certain company can use this model

This is because it is only preferable for use by companies whose HR team is on the same page with the strategy of the business. There are more other models of HRM that can be used for the company to improve or solve the problem of the company.

Form these benefits and drawbacks. Syarikat Al Rasyid should try to implement the Standard casual model of HRM as there are more benefits from them than the drawbacks. Even though it cannot solve all of the problems that Syarikat Al Rasyid has been dealt with.

Conclusion

To conclude the report, Standard casual of HRM model is a good model which can be used for a company that their HR is on the same page with the business strategy. For Syarikat Al Rasyid if they do implement this model it would not solve all their problems but it is still a good choice for them to implement it. This Standard casual of HRM model is well known because this model is the combination of all models from the 90s to early 2000s.

(2,338 words)

References

Erik van Vulpen, (2020, May 13). *5 Human Resources Models Every HR Practitioner Should Know*. AIHR Digital. Retrieve from: <https://www.digitalhrtech.com/human-resources-models/>.

Heathfield, S. M. *What Is Human Resource Management? The Balance Careers*. Retrieve from: <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/what-is-human-resource-management-1918143>.

Human Resource Management - What is HRM? - Definitions - Functions - Objectives - Importance - Evolution of HRM from Personnel management. What is Human Resource? (Defined) Human Resource Management Topics - Labour Laws - High Courts & Supreme Court Citation - Case Laws. Retrieve from: <http://www.whatishumanresource.com/human-resource-management>.

Kenton, W. (2020, September 16). *Reading Financial Performance*. Investopedia. Retrieve from: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/financialperformance.asp>.

Long, J. (2014, September 2). *8 Musts to Start Your Business With Little to No Capital*. Entrepreneur. Retrieve from: <https://www.entrepreneur.com/slideshow/299697>.

Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.

Nicasio, F. (2020, August 3). *How to Increase Your Profit Margins: 10 Strategies to improve Profitability*. Vend Retail Blog. Retrieve from:
<https://www.vendhq.com/blog/increase-profit-margins/>.

The 6Q Blog, (2019, August 2). *5 Human Resources Models Every HR Practitioner Should Know*. Retrieve from: <https://inside.6q.io/5-human-resources-models/>.

The Standard Causal Model of HRM. Glossary. Retrieve from:
<https://www.peoplehum.com/glossary/the-standard-causal-model-of-hrm>.